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FEATURES OF THE USE OF INNOVATIVE AND TRADITIONAL METHODS IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

Akhrorova Amira Aminovna

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ABSTRACT

As part of the globalization process, to learn foreign languages is becoming more and more obvious every day. When teaching a foreign language, a special place is occupied by classes that contribute to the development of personal qualities, stimulate development and ensure the formation of interest in learning a foreign language.

As part of the globalization process, to learn foreign languages is becoming more and more obvious every day. When teaching a foreign language, a special place is occupied by classes that contribute to the development of personal qualities, stimulate development and ensure the formation of interest in learning a foreign language. Currently, there are a lot of methods and approaches in teaching foreign languages. But it should be noted that the methods of teaching foreign languages are constantly changing. As the prominent linguist A.A. Mirolubov, it is impossible to interest students, increase their motivation, arouse their interest, relying only on old methods. Before comparing them and coming to a final opinion, let's describe and compare them with each other.

A lecture is a method by which a lecturer verbally conveys one or another practical and theoretical topic in an expanded form. In order to conduct lectures, a teacher must not only have a good knowledge of the topic, but also have extensive practical and pedagogical experience. That is why only a well-trained specialist in his field can give lectures. According to their content and nature, lectures are divided into the following types:

1. Introductory lecture
2. Overview lecture
3. Problem lecture
4. Information lecture

An introductory lecture is given to students who are not at all familiar with a particular lecture, this is an acquaintance of students with a whole section of the subject being studied. An overview lecture is aimed at summarizing and expanding students' knowledge of a particular subject. A problem lecture is held to attract students' attention to solving conflicting problems. An information lecture is characterized only by the fact that the teacher must present information orally and familiarize all students with the topic. Lectures are

usually held for students in higher education institutions and students have to listen to the whole speech of the lecturer until the end of the class, within 1-1.5 hours. This is very tiring not only for the lecturer but also for the students. From the beginning to the end of the lesson, the lecturer verbally covers the topic and thus the students should listen and take notes to themselves so that, during the seminar, they could respond.

Text translation. The students' are given a text and the teacher sets the task to translate it from beginning to end. Translation of the text can be carried out:

- Orally;
- Written

Orally, students read the text one by one and translate it orally into Russian, thereby developing their speech. This also very effectively improves not only the listening, but also the reading of students.

In writing, the teacher gives the task to the students to translate the text to them in writing, but before giving them this, he will familiarize them with the new words that are in the text and within 20-25 minutes the students translate the text according to the meaning. After that, the teacher asks questions about the text. The students respond.

The method of "**quiet**" learning is one of the well-known methods, the author of which is K. Gatten. In his opinion, the initiative in the lesson should come primarily from students, since most of the study time is occupied by a student, and the teacher's task is to use a foreign language as often as possible and overcome language barriers. But it is worth noting that the use of "quiet" learning has its limitations, because it assumes a high degree of student interest and awakening motivation, which is not always able to manifest in students in secondary schools. The advantage of the method is to stimulate students' motivation in the learning process of various supports and visual aids. Another of the traditional teaching methods is the "method of communicative tasks", which is the solution of communicative tasks. During the lesson, the teacher gives a specific task on the topic covered, students perform speech and non-speech actions, thereby come into contact with each other and try to find the right ways to solve the task set by the teacher. The advantage of this method is not only speech, but also physical actions, gestures, facial expressions, which motivate students not only to solve the problem, but also to improve their spoken language. Textbooks designed and compiled in accordance with this method consist of communicative tasks, while students during the lesson must solve the problem posed by their teacher.

The grammar -translation method, which was widely known in Europe when teaching Latin, and at the end of the XIX century became popular as a method of teaching modern languages such as French, German and English. It is also called the "Prussian method" in the USA. The main task of teaching is reading literature, since its purpose is to develop logical thinking and intelligence in students. The disadvantages of this method is that special attention is paid only to written speech, oral speech is not provided.

Listening and speaking part serve as a means of learning. Students are given texts to read, a bilingual dictionary is widely used, exercises for translating from a foreign language into their native language. The main goal is to translate the exercises, exam assignments in writing.

Cluster is an effective method for critical thinking in foreign language lessons. The rules are very simple. The teacher puts the topic in the center, and the students thereby have to find

everything that concerns the topic and make a chain between the main and dependent words. I would like to note that the cluster system covers a large amount of information. This is an ideal way to make students' thought processes visual. Sometimes the cluster is also called "visual brainstorming". This method helps students to gather their thoughts in a certain order. I think that the cluster is indispensable when working with vocabulary in foreign language lessons. The advantage of the cluster is that students can work with this method not only on an interactive whiteboard, but also in the form of presentation protection, in pairs, in groups, as well as individually.

When working with clusters, the following basic rules must be observed:

- let your imagination run wild;
- continue until the time set by the teacher runs out;
- try to build as many connections as possible;
- do not follow a predetermined plan.

The method looks simple, but nevertheless is very effective in teaching foreign languages.

An innovative method. The project methodology is an individual and group activity of students, which includes independent work on a specific topic in the form of a presentation, report and poster work. Students are given a specific topic, during which they encounter a number of problems, since this method is new to them. The project methodology is used in foreign language lessons and thus includes working in groups under the guidance of a teacher. The advantages of the project methodology are:

- the ability to communicate with students for joint and timely completion of tasks in a foreign language;
- the possibility of motivation in order to win over the other groups;
- ability to work with Internet resources and literature to find the necessary information;
- development of students' independence;
- creating and protecting a presentation in the classroom;
- development of creative abilities of students.

It is believed that the project methodology is best used for high school, but simple projects can be used even for 7-8 classics. For designing, students should be given 2-3 lessons, during which students will search for information and create their presentations, then plan how to protect their work in the classroom. All students participate in the implementation of the project in the lesson, each group consists of no more than 4 people. Students do most of the work in the classroom. These include the following:

- search and collection of information;
- design of the material yourself;
- presentation of the project;
- summing up the results.

The task of the teacher is to build the work in such a way that students need additional information, which contributes to the independent search for material. This thereby teaches students to be independent, demonstrate their results, defend their project, answer questions from another group, prove their point of view and explain their choice. The question arises, what difficulties do students face when designing a job? It is difficult for students to agree among themselves, as many people have more thoughts. Not all participants do their part. But

all these difficulties are surmountable. Over time, students will get used to this method and will be able to work successfully not only in groups, but also individually. As for correcting mistakes, in this case, the teacher does not interrupt, makes notes to himself, i.e. writes down the gross mistakes of the student and at the end of the lesson, when summing up, corrects the mistakes. In general, the project methodology in teaching foreign languages is an important stage not only for the development of speech skills, but also for the development of students' independence.

E-mail is an indispensable tool to attract the attention of students. This method is best used at the senior level of training. How to use this method? The teacher sends a letter to the student on a certain topic and leaves it unfinished. The student who received the letter adds 2-3 sentences, then sends it to another student, that student reads the text and adds his own several sentences according to the meaning and sends it to the next one, and this continues until the letter is returned to the teacher. The resulting story is read and evaluated by the teacher according to the following parameters:

- spelling;
- grammar;
- logic;
- vocabulary;
- context;
- humor.

The advantages of this method are:

- ability to think logically;
- improve your written speech;
- formalize an unprepared statement;
- improve vocabulary.

It is allowed to choose topics not only from the main sections of the textbook, but also from other resources that are relevant and interesting for students.

The communicative method is the acquisition of communicative competence by students. The teacher gives texts on a certain topic and there are debates on this topic. The subject of the text encourages students to express their opinions. And it should be noted that the process does not take place against the background of grammar, but is carried out by communicative intentions. The student finds himself in the learning center.

The advantages of this method are:

- students improve their oral speech skills;
- overcome fear - don't make mistakes;
- free communication in a foreign language.

I would like to note that high-quality training of students is impossible without modern methods and approaches.

The next innovative method is the "**role-playing**" method, which is widely known in Europe. The method helps students to develop skills and abilities in the field of communication ability. The teacher gives different topics, for example, at the doctor, in the store or at an interview. The work is carried out in pairs. The teacher gives time to prepare. Students choose a topic and compose different dialogues in a foreign language and thereby enter the role. If you have

chosen the topic "Interview", one of the students acts as an employer, and the other as an employee. Then they present their roles in a foreign language.

Role-playing helps students:

- overcome language barriers;
- increases the volume of speech activity;
- stimulates and motivates.

In general, the method of "role-playing" is very interesting and effective in improving the spoken language of students in a foreign language.

It is worth noting that information technology is not the only way to increase motivation and independence of students when learning foreign languages. One of the effective methods is the language portfolio. This is a set of working materials of students from the experience and practice that they have accumulated in the process of learning a foreign language. The portfolio that they have collected for the entire learning process not only helps them to evaluate what has been done, but also to analyze the work that they have done throughout the training to achieve their goals. A briefcase is called a "case" in another way.

The case is a single information complex, which consists of:

- necessary information;
- specific situation;
- tasks in the form of answers to questions.

Students' work with the case includes several stages:

- preparatory;
- main;
- the final one.

At the preparatory stage, the teacher stimulates the goals and objectives of each stage. The main stage consists of solving and discussing problems. At the final stage, the results are summed up.

In conclusion, it should be noted that there are as many innovative methods as there are traditional ones. In the process of teaching, the teacher decides which method is best for him to use, since it is he who is more familiar with the audience, equipment, number of students, textbook and student abilities than anyone else. But do not forget that the main task of a teacher is to train comprehensively developed and highly qualified specialists.

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